

1 **Residential exposure to green and blue spaces over childhood and cardiometabolic health outcomes:**
2 **The Generation XXI birth cohort**

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13 **Keywords:** green space, blue space, cardiometabolic health, obesity, blood pressure, metabolic syndrome

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29 **Abstract**

30 Evidence on the effects of green and blue spaces on childhood cardiometabolic health is inconsistent and
31 mostly cross-sectional. We assessed the associations of green and blue spaces exposure at birth 4, 7, and 10
32 years (to identify vulnerable periods of exposure) and as longitudinal trajectories (to identify the longitudinal
33 effect over time) with cardiometabolic outcomes at 10 years.

34 Among 4669 participants from a population-based birth cohort, we assessed the residential normalized
35 difference vegetation index (NDVI) and distance to urban green and blue spaces at each time point using
36 geographic information systems and standardized by dividing the observed value by the standard deviation.
37 Longitudinal exposure trajectories were derived using latent class mixed models. At 10 years, we measured
38 body mass index, fat mass index, android-to-gynoid fat ratio, blood pressure, and metabolic outcomes. We
39 defined overweight/obesity (World Health Organization), high blood pressure (American Academy of
40 Pediatrics), and metabolic syndrome (IDEFICS).

41 No significant associations were observed between natural spaces exposure and adiposity outcomes. We
42 found an inverse association between distance to nearest blue space at birth and systolic blood pressure z-
43 scores, and a positive association between distance to nearest green space at 7 and 10 years and metabolic
44 syndrome score ($p < 0.05$). Children in the descending NDVI500m trajectory, compared to those in the high
45 stable trajectory, showed lower diastolic blood pressure z-scores and metabolic syndrome scores ($p < 0.05$).
46 However, after multiple testing corrections, all associations lost statistical significance.

47 This study did not find robust associations between natural spaces during key developmental periods and
48 cardiometabolic health.

49 **Key words:** green space, blue space, cardiometabolic health, obesity, blood pressure, metabolic syndrome

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53 **Introduction**

54 Urban green and blue spaces have been associated with salutogenic effects¹⁻³, including promoting
55 physical activity^{4,5}, improving psychological well-being^{4,6-8}, reducing environmental hazards⁷, and fostering
56 social interactions.^{4,9} While exposure to urban green and blue spaces has been shown to be protective in
57 adulthood against cardiometabolic, respiratory, and neurodevelopmental morbidity and mortality^{1,10},
58 evidence in childhood remains limited.¹¹

59 Global prevalence of overweight/obesity and high blood pressure (BP) in childhood is estimated to
60 be up to 18%¹² and 9.7%¹³, respectively. When co-occurring alongside dyslipidemia and hyperglycemia,
61 these conditions can culminate in metabolic syndrome (MetS), which accounts for a global prevalence in
62 children and adolescents of 3.3%¹⁴ – further increasing the risk of cardiovascular disease in adulthood.¹⁵
63 Previous studies on the influence of exposure to green and blue spaces on overweight/obesity and high BP in
64 childhood show mixed results.¹⁶⁻³⁵ While the proximity to blue spaces has been associated with lower odds
65 of childhood overweight and obesity,^{32,33} studies on green spaces exposure have reported protective^{17-19,28-31}
66 but also adverse^{36,37} or no²³⁻²⁶ effects on obesity. Previous studies reported that greater exposure to greenness
67 around children's schools^{22,34,35,38} and residences²¹ was associated with lower BP. Conversely, a study within
68 the HELIX, a European consortium of six birth cohorts, found no association of green and blue spaces with
69 paediatric BP.²⁰ A recent individual-participant data meta-analysis comprising 10 European cohorts found no
70 association between green space and body mass index (BMI) and BP during childhood.³⁹ To the best of our
71 knowledge, no study has yet explored the influence of urban natural spaces on childhood body fat content
72 and distribution, which is a better predictor of health risk than BMI, as well as on MetS.

73 The existing studies differ in the methodological definition of natural space exposure. While those
74 examining blue spaces focus on coastal distance^{32,33}, studies on urban green spaces use a variety of exposure
75 measures, such as greenness (Normalized Difference Vegetation Index)^{16,17,20,21,26,27,30,38}, street tree density
76^{29,35}, park access^{19,23}, area^{27,29} and proximity^{19,26,28,30}, as well as the percentage of urban green spaces^{16,31} and
77 time spent in green spaces²⁴, using them either in isolation or combination. Additionally, most of the
78 mentioned studies are cross-sectional^{17,19,21,23-30,32-35,38} and do not explore the potential cumulative effects and

79 the time-variability of green and blue space exposures.⁴⁰ Therefore, adopting a life-course approach and
80 assessing exposure to green and blue spaces over childhood will not only account for cumulative effects but
81 may also identify periods of vulnerability during early-life.⁴¹

82 We aimed to investigate the associations of exposure to green and blue spaces at birth, 4, 7 and 10
83 years and as trajectories from birth until 10 years, with BMI, body fat content and fat distribution, BP and
84 MetS in children aged 10 years. We specifically aimed to identify vulnerable periods of exposure and the
85 longitudinal effect over time. We hypothesized that a greater exposure to residential green and blue spaces
86 from birth through late childhood is associated with improved cardiometabolic health at 10 years.

87

88 **Methods**

89 *Study participants*

90 This study is embedded within the Generation XXI (G21), a birth cohort from Porto Metropolitan
91 Area, Portugal. G21 comprises 8495 mothers and 8647 newborns recruited between April 2005 and August
92 2006 in all five existing public maternity units. During the hospital stay, mothers who delivered live births
93 with at least 24 gestational weeks were invited to participate in the study, of whom 92% agreed. Participants
94 were re-evaluated at 4, 7, and 10 years of age (86%, 80%, and 74% participation rates, respectively). More
95 cohort details were published elsewhere.^{42,43} In this study, we included singletons with complete information
96 on exposure to urban natural spaces at birth, 4, 7, and 10 years (n=7549). From those, we excluded children
97 without any information on cardiometabolic outcomes at 10 years and on covariates. Thus, 4669 children
98 were included in the analysis (Figure S1).

99 All phases of the study complied with the Ethical Principles for Medical Research Involving Human
100 Subjects expressed in the Declaration of Helsinki.⁴⁴ The baseline and follow-up evaluations until 10 years
101 were approved by the University of Porto Medical School/ S. João Hospital Centre Ethics Committee. At
102 baseline and follow-up evaluations, all procedures were explained to participants, and an informed consent
103 was signed by one of the parents or legal guardians. The baseline evaluation was additionally approved by

104 the Data Protection National Commission, and the study follows the present EU General Data Protection
105 Regulation under the close supervision of the Data Protection Office of ISPUP.

106

107 *Study area*

108 Porto Metropolitan Area is the second largest metropolitan area of the country with almost 1.3 million
109 inhabitants.⁴⁵ It is in the northwest region of Continental Portugal and is limited by the Atlantic Coast and
110 extends along the Douro River estuary. Although Porto Metropolitan Area is constituted by 17 municipalities
111 spread over almost 2.040 km², 6 of them comprise nearly 85% of its population (N = 1,112,555 inhabitants)
112 - Porto, Matosinhos, Maia, Vila Nova de Gaia, Gondomar, and Valongo.⁴⁵ Over the years, these
113 municipalities experienced urbanization at different rates.⁴⁶ Porto, for example, turned from a “green city”
114 with 76% green areas in 1892 to a much more “grey city” with 29% green areas remaining by 2000.⁴⁷

115

116 *Urban natural spaces at birth, 4, 7 and 10 years*

117 Birth and 4, 7 and 10 years, corresponding to preschool, the first cycle and the second cycle of
118 elementary school, respectively, represent critical windows in children’s development. During these stages,
119 their physiological, neurological, and immune systems undergo significant maturation, making them
120 particularly vulnerable to environmental exposures that might impact their long-term health.⁴⁸ In particular,
121 at age 4, children are approaching adiposity rebound, a key stage in body fat development linked to later
122 obesity and metabolic health⁴⁹ and the ages 7 and 10 precede and mark the onset of declines in cardiovascular
123 health trajectories, respectively.⁵⁰

124 At each evaluation, the residential address history was updated. Then, the self-reported residential
125 addresses were processed and georeferenced using ArcGIS Online World Geocoding Service and Google
126 Earth.

127 *Greenness*

128 Surrounding greenness was estimated using the normalized difference vegetation index (NDVI),
129 which represents the density of vegetation within 100m, 250m, and 500m of the child’s residence. Different

130 buffers were used to cover immediate and more distant areas of exposure.⁵¹ NDVI was calculated based on
131 land surface reflectance of visible red and near-infrared wavelengths. The values range from -1 (water) to 0
132 (rock, sand, and snow) and 1 (photosynthetically active and healthy vegetation), with higher positive values
133 indicating denser green vegetation. In this study, negative NDVI values were omitted from the calculation.
134 The NDVI exposure assessment was based on the average value during the spring and summer months.
135 Specifically, only images with $\leq 5\%$ of cloud coverage from Landsat 5 and 8 (spatial resolution: 30 m) during
136 the spring/summer period (peak of vegetation) of the assessment years (2005/2006, 2009/2011, 2012/2014,
137 and 2015/2017) were used, as previously described in G21 cohort studies.^{52,53} ArcMap 10.5 was used to
138 process satellite images, and QGIS 3.8 was used to extract the average NDVI.

139

140 *Residential distance to the nearest urban green space*

141 The Euclidean distance (in hectometres) from the child's residential address to the nearest urban
142 green space (UGS) was measured during the G21 cohort evaluations. UGS referred to all public and free-to-
143 access UGS in the Porto Metropolitan Area (n=662), regardless of size, location, or specific characteristics,
144 namely public parks, gardens, and other green spaces managed by city councils of Porto Metropolitan Area
145 or privately owned but freely accessible. Cartography was obtained from digital maps provided by the city
146 halls of the Porto Metropolitan Area. When UGS were fenced, the distance to the entrance was used;
147 otherwise, the distance to the nearest boundary was considered. ArcGIS version 10.5 and the Network Analyst
148 extension were used for calculations, applying an updated street network dataset provided by the
149 Environmental Systems Research Institute.

150 *Residential distance to the nearest urban blue space*

151 The Euclidean distance (in hectometres) from the child's residential address to the nearest river or
152 sea was measured during the G21 cohort evaluations using the Portuguese Water Atlas (from the Portuguese
153 "*Atlas da Água*"). The Portuguese Water Atlas was developed by the National Water Resources Information
154 System (SNIRH) under the responsibility of the Portuguese Environment Agency. The SNIRH provides

155 information on hydrometeorological variables and water quality (surface, groundwater, and coastal) through
156 the network of water resource monitoring stations in Portugal. In this study, other types of blue spaces, such
157 as fountains, ponds and lakes were not included due to their small size.

158

159 ***Cardiometabolic outcomes at 10 years***

160 *Body mass index, body fat content and distribution*

161 Height was measured using a stadiometer (SECA 206 Hamburg, Germany®) to the nearest 0.1 cm,
162 and weight with a digital scale (TANITA® model TBF 300) to the nearest 0.1 kg, while the child stood
163 barefooted in underwear. BMI was calculated as weight (kg)/height (m)² and then converted into standard
164 deviation (SD) scores (BMI z-scores), adjusted for age and sex using the World Health Organization (WHO)
165 growth reference values.⁵⁴ The WHO cut-offs were applied, and the following BMI z-score categories were
166 defined: <-2 SDs for underweight, -2 ≤ SD ≤ 1 for normal weight, 1 > SD ≤ 2 for overweight, and >2 SDs
167 for obesity⁵⁴. For models focused on the risk of overweight/obesity, children with underweight were excluded,
168 and those with overweight and obesity were combined.

169 We measured total body fat mass and android and gynoid fat mass by whole-body dual-energy X-
170 ray absorptiometry (DXA) scans using a Hologic Discovery QDR 4500W device (Hologic Inc., Bedford,
171 Massachusetts) and following the standard manufacturer's protocol, with the child in underwear and with an
172 emptied bladder.⁵⁵ We divided total fat mass by height⁴ to obtain a fat mass index (FMI) uncorrelated with
173 height after estimating the optimal adjustment through log-regression analyses.⁵⁶ We also calculated the
174 android-to-gynoid fat ratio by dividing android by gynoid fat mass.

175 *Blood pressure*

176 Systolic Blood Pressure (SBP) and Diastolic Blood Pressure (DBP) were measured with an aneroid
177 sphygmomanometer (Erka Vario Desk Model), using a stethoscope placed over the brachial artery pulse,
178 proximal and medial to the cubital fossa, and below the bottom edge of the cuff (i.e., 2 cm above the cubital
179 fossa), while the child was seated.^{57,58} Three measurements were taken, and the mean of the last two
180 measurements was considered. Then, age -, sex -, and height-specific z-scores and percentiles of SBP and

181 DBP were calculated following the recommendations of the American Academy of Pediatrics, and high BP
182 was defined when mean SBP and/or DBP $\geq 90^{\text{th}}$ percentile.⁵⁷

183 *Metabolic outcomes*

184 Waist circumference measurements were taken to the nearest 0.1 cm at the umbilicus level with the
185 child in a standing position, with the abdomen relaxed, arms at the sides, and feet positioned together. After
186 an overnight fast, a venous blood sample was collected before 11 am. Glucose was measured using ultraviolet
187 (UV) enzymatic assay (hexokinase method), insulin was measured using electrochemiluminescence
188 immunoassay, and triglycerides and high-density lipoprotein cholesterol (HDL cholesterol) were measured
189 using an enzymatic colorimetric assay. Homeostatic model assessment-insulin resistance (HOMA-IR) was
190 calculated as glucose (mg/dL) x insulin (mU/mL)/405.⁵⁹ Age- and sex-specific percentiles for each parameter
191 were obtained according to the IDEFICS Study¹⁵. MetS was defined as having ≥ 3 of the following criteria:
192 excess adiposity (waist circumference $\geq 90^{\text{th}}$ percentile), high blood pressure (SBP and/or DBP $\geq 90^{\text{th}}$
193 percentile), dyslipidemia (triglycerides $\geq 90^{\text{th}}$ or HDL $\leq 10^{\text{th}}$ percentile) and hyperglycemia (HOMA-IR $\geq 90^{\text{th}}$
194 percentile or fasting glucose $\geq 90^{\text{th}}$ percentile).¹⁵ Additionally, a continuous MetS score combining the
195 components of the MetS was calculated, in which higher score levels indicate a worse metabolic profile.¹⁵

196 **Covariates**

197 Covariates related to both the urban natural spaces exposures and cardiometabolic outcomes were
198 defined according to the literature and depicted in a directed acyclic graph (Figure S2). Maternal educational
199 level reported at birth was measured as the number of completed years of formal schooling and classified
200 according to the International Standard Classification of Education 2011 into low (0-9 years), medium (10-
201 12 years), and high education (>12 years).⁶⁰ Neighbourhood socioeconomic deprivation index was
202 categorized into quintiles, with the first quintile to the least deprived and the fifth quintile to the most
203 deprived.⁶¹ Nitrogen dioxide (NO₂) and particulate matter less than 2.5 μm (PM_{2.5}) were calculated using
204 the land use regression (LUR) modelling approach, developed in the European Study of Cohorts for Air
205 Pollution Effects (ESCAPE) framework 2009, and temporal adjustment was conducted using background

206 routine monitoring stations. Neighbourhood socioeconomic deprivation index, NO₂ and PM2.5. were
207 available at birth, 4, 7, and 10 years of age.

208

209 **Statistical analysis**

210 A descriptive analysis of the study population and a comparative analysis between participants and
211 non-participants were performed. The correlation between green and blue space exposures, for each and
212 across time-points, was examined and visually displayed using a heat map.

213 We used latent class mixed models (R package lcmm) to develop trajectories of urban natural space
214 exposures from birth until 10 years of age, using a sample with complete data on green and blue space
215 exposure at all time points (n=7549) (Figure S1).⁶² The Bayesian Information Criteria (BIC) and the Akaike
216 Information Criteria (AIC) were used to identify the optimal number of trajectory groups, and then the mean
217 posterior probability of participants belonging to each latent class was analysed.⁶³ We modelled the
218 association of surrounding greenness (NDVI 100m, 250m, and 500m) and distance to the nearest urban green
219 and blue spaces, at each time point and as longitudinal trajectories, with BMI, SBP and DBP z-scores and
220 MetS score, continuously, using linear regression models (beta coefficients (β) along with their 95%
221 confidence intervals (CI)), and with overweight/obesity, high BP and MetS, as binary outcomes, at 10 years,
222 using logistic regression models (odds ratios (OR), 95% CI). We assessed non-linear relationships between
223 exposures and outcomes using Generalized Additive Models (GAMs). The GAMs results were similar to
224 those from linear models and incorporating non-linearity reduced interpretability and risked overfitting.
225 Therefore, we found no consistent evidence of non-linear associations and presented the results from the
226 linear models. Additionally, we assessed the associations of the urban natural space exposures, at each time
227 point and as longitudinal trajectories, with the fat mass index and android-to-gynoid fat ratio using linear
228 regression models. For the analyses with fat mass index, and due to its skewed distribution, we observed a
229 violation of the normality of the residuals' assumption in the linear regression models, and thus we log-
230 transformed fat mass index and presented the exponential β and their 95% CI. For each regression analysis,
231 we developed crude and adjusted models, including the aforementioned covariates. In the analyses looking

232 at the associations of exposures per time point, we adjusted for the neighbourhood socioeconomic deprivation
233 index, NO₂, and PM2.5. at each respective time point. In the analyses looking at the associations of the
234 trajectories of exposure, due to the high correlation of these environmental data over childhood, we only used
235 information at birth and 10 years. To facilitate the interpretation of effect estimates and to enable comparisons
236 in effect size, we standardized [observed value/standard deviation] the continuous environmental exposures
237 and continuous covariates (PM2.5. and NO₂). We tested for statistical interactions with child's sex, maternal
238 education, and neighbourhood deprivation index in all models, but none of the interaction terms were
239 statistically significant (p-values > 0.05). We performed sensitivity analyses focused on each of the individual
240 components of the MetS, namely glucose, HOMA-IR, triglycerides, HDL, and waist circumference as
241 continuous z-scores. Due to the high number of tests performed, we corrected for multiple testing using the
242 False Discovery Rate (FDR) method.⁶⁴ All analyses were performed in R software version 4.2.0.

243 **Results**

244 *Study participants*

245 Description of exposure to green and blue spaces from birth until 10 years of age is presented in
246 Tables 1 and S1. The levels of surrounding greenness and distance to the nearest green and blue space showed
247 a small increase from birth until 10 years of age. The mean (SD) NDVI within a buffer of 100m, 250m and
248 500m ranged from 0.16 (0.08) at birth to 0.21 (0.06) at 10 years old, from 0.20 (0.07) to 0.24 (0.06), and from
249 0.22 (0.07) to 0.25 (0.06), respectively. The median (25th-75th percentile) distance to the nearest green or blue
250 space, from birth until 10 years, ranged from 9.24 (4.94-15.07) hm to 9.53 (5.15-15.19) hm, and from 18.43
251 (10.44-29.99) hm to 18.85 (10.78-30.39) hm, respectively (Table 1). At each time point, correlations between
252 residential distance to the nearest blue space with residential distance to the nearest green space and
253 surrounding greenness were very low (<0.05) and low (0.10-0.30), respectively (Figure S3). Low to moderate
254 correlations were found between the distance to the nearest green space and surrounding greenness (0.25-
255 0.45). Considering the green and blue space exposures at different time points, moderate to strong correlations
256 were found (0.60-0.95).

257 Participants' characteristics regarding covariates and outcomes are shown in Table 2. Females
258 comprise 48.9% of the sample. At 10 years, the prevalence of childhood overweight/obesity, high BP, and
259 MetS was 43.4%, 26.5%, and 17.5%, respectively.

260 As compared to non-participants, participants had a greater residential distance to the nearest blue
261 space, exhibited a higher exposure to NO₂ and PM2.5., were less likely to live in a more deprived
262 neighbourhood, and their mothers had a higher educational level (Table S2).

263

264 *Urban natural spaces per time point and cardiometabolic outcomes*

265 Table 3 shows the associations between green and blue spaces at each time point and the
266 cardiometabolic health outcomes at 10 years. We observed an inverse association between the residential
267 distance to the nearest blue space at birth and SBP z-scores at 10 years [β (95%CI) = -0.02 (-0.05; -0.00) SBP
268 z-score per each standard deviation of distance]. Additionally, a positive association between the residential
269 distance to the nearest green space at 7 and 10 years with MetS score at 10 years was found [β (95%CI) =
270 0.13 (0.01;0.26) and 0.14 (0.01;0.27) MetS score per each standard deviation of distance, respectively].
271 However, after correction for multiple testing, all these associations lost statistical significance. We did not
272 find any statistically significant association for BMI z-score, DBP z-score, overweight/obesity, high BP, or
273 MetS at 10 years, and for the surrounding greenness at birth, 4, 7, and 10 years with any of the outcomes.
274 The crude associations are depicted in the supplementary material (Table S3). No statistically significant
275 associations were observed between green and blue spaces at each time point and the fat mass index and
276 android-to-gynoid fat ratio (Table S4).

277

278 *Urban natural spaces exposure trajectories*

279 The values of AIC and BIC used to identify the optimal number of trajectory groups and the mean
280 posterior probability of participants belonging to each latent class are depicted in Tables S5 and S6,
281 respectively. We identified the following distinct trajectories from birth to 10 years: A) for NDVI within

282 100m: 1) high stable (n=747) and 2) low ascending (n=3922); B) for NDVI within 250m: 1) high stable
283 (n=1091), 2) low ascending (n=3223), 3) ascending (n=207), 4) descending (n=148); C) for NDVI within
284 500m: 1) high stable (n=1287), 2) low ascending (n=3007), 3) ascending (n=227), 4) descending (n=148);
285 D) for the distance to the nearest green space: 1) medium stable (n=4396), 2) ascending (n=137), 3)
286 descending (n=136); and E) for the distance to the nearest blue space: 1) high stable (n=4141), 2) low stable
287 (n=528) (Figure 1, Table S7).

288

289 *Urban natural spaces exposure trajectories and cardiometabolic outcomes*

290 Table 4 shows the associations between green and blue spaces exposure trajectories and the
291 cardiometabolic health outcomes at 10 years. We observed that, as compared to children in the high stable
292 trajectory of NDVI within 500m, those in the descending trajectory of NDVI within 500m presented a lower
293 DBP z-score at 10 years [β (95%CI) = -0.15 (-0.26; -0.04)] as well as a lower MetS score at 10 years [β
294 (95%CI) = -0.72 (-1.38; -0.07)]. Nonetheless, after correction for multiple testing, these associations lost
295 statistical significance. We did not find any statistically significant association for any other cardiometabolic
296 outcome at 10 years and any other green and blue spaces exposure trajectory. The crude associations are
297 depicted in the supplementary material (Table S8). No statistically significant associations were observed
298 between green and blue spaces exposure trajectories and the fat mass index and android-to-gynoid fat ratio
299 (Table S9).

300

301 **Sensitivity analysis**

302 Tables S10 and S11 show the associations of exposure to green and blue spaces at each time point
303 and as longitudinal trajectories, respectively, with each of the individual components of the MetS at 10 years
304 as continuous z-scores. We observed that higher distance to the nearest blue space at birth, 4, 7, and 10 years
305 was associated with lower glucose z-scores, while higher distance to the nearest green space at 4 years was
306 associated with higher HOMA-IR z-scores (p-values<0.05). We also observed that a higher distance to the
307 nearest blue space at 7 years was associated with lower triglycerides z-scores, and higher surrounding

308 greenness within 250m at 10 years was associated with lower HDL cholesterol z-scores (p-values<0.05).
309 Additionally, we observed that, as compared to children in the low stable trajectory of distance to the nearest
310 blue space, those in the high stable trajectory presented lower glucose z-scores and as compared to children
311 in the high stable trajectory of NDVI within 500m, those in the descending trajectory presented lower waist
312 circumference z-scores (p-values<0.05). All these associations lost statistical significance after correction for
313 multiple testing.

314

315 **Discussion**

316 This study did not support our hypothesis that a greater exposure to green and blue spaces is
317 associated with better cardiometabolic health in childhood. We did not observe significant associations of
318 urban green and blue spaces with body mass index, body fat content, and fat distribution at 10 years. The
319 observed associations for blood pressure and metabolic outcomes were of small magnitude, not present after
320 correction for multiple testing, and were not consistently observed across time points and between trajectories
321 for continuous and dichotomic outcomes

322 Two previous longitudinal studies with large sample sizes - 51,873 children and adolescents aged 6
323 to 19 years old in the United States of America and 79,992 children followed-up until 5 years old in Spain -
324 have shown associations between increased NDVI and decreased BMI z-scores.^{16,18} Likewise, a cross-
325 sectional study using data from the 2018 Health Behaviour in School-aged Children (HBSC) Italian survey,
326 among a regionally representative sample of 2065 Italian adolescents aged 11 to 13 years, found that higher
327 exposure to NDVI was associated with a lower risk of obesity.¹⁶ Two cross-sectional studies among 1,489
328 Lithuania's children and 442 Turkish children have found no significant association between the distance to
329 the nearest green space and the risk of overweight or obesity^{25,26}, while a cross-sectional study including 440
330 primary school children aged 6-13 years old in Kathmandu metropolitan city (Nepal) found a higher risk of
331 overweight and obesity among children whose residence was > 1km from the nearest green space.¹⁹ In an
332 individual-participant data (IPD) meta-analysis of over 35,000 children across eight countries, residential
333 green space exposure using NDVI within a 300m buffer and proximity to green spaces during prenatal and

334 childhood periods were not associated with BMI z-scores.³⁹ Further studies that defined green space by
335 caregiver-reported access to parks and recreational spaces²³ or by time spent in green spaces²⁴ found no
336 association with BMI. On the other hand, a Norwegian cross-sectional study with 10,527 participants aged
337 between 14 and 16 years found that the odds of having overweight were 1.38 times higher for those living in
338 the greenest areas compared to those in the least green areas.³⁶ Studies looking at the exposure to blue spaces
339 concerning body mass index are scarce. Baseline data from the Whole of Systems Trial of Prevention
340 Strategies for Childhood Obesity (WHOSTOPS), with data from 1216 children aged 8.5-13 years, found that
341 girls living closer to the coastal area had lower odds of having overweight/obesity.^{32,33} In the present study,
342 we found no significant association of surrounding greenness and residential distance to the nearest green or
343 blue space at any time point and when using trajectories from birth to 10 years with BMI z-score,
344 overweight/obesity, and body fat content and distribution.

345 Cross-sectional studies from Austria³⁵, Italy³⁵, China^{34,65} and Germany²¹, from 1251 to 588,004
346 children and adolescents samples, showed that higher greenness around school^{34,35} and residence²¹ was
347 associated with lower systolic^{4,34,35} and diastolic blood pressure^{21,34}, reduced odds of hypertension³⁴, whereas
348 reduced greenness was associated with higher blood pressure.²¹ A Chinese longitudinal and dynamic cohort
349 of children and adolescents (2005-2018) found that a decrease in greenness around schools was associated
350 with higher blood pressure.²² Yet, other studies did not find such associations. The HELIX study, comprising
351 4279 children aged 4 to 5 years old, found that neither the exposure to NDVI (100m, 300m, 500m) nor the
352 distance to the nearest major green and blue space during pregnancy were significantly related with both
353 systolic and diastolic blood pressure in middle-childhood.²⁰ Similarly, the Childhood and Adolescence
354 Surveillance and Prevention of Adult Non-communicable disease study [CASPIA-IV] (2015) – which
355 included 12 340 children aged 7 to 18 years old, living in urban and rural areas of Iran, found no association
356 between subjective proximity to green spaces (perception of having access to such spaces within a 15-minute
357 walk from their home) and systolic and diastolic blood pressure.⁶⁶ The previously mentioned IPD meta-
358 analysis also did not find an association between residential green space exposure and systolic and diastolic
359 blood pressure.³⁹ In the present study, after correction for multiple testing, no associations were observed

360 between surrounding greenness and residential distance to the nearest green or blue space at any time point
361 and when using trajectories from birth to 10 years with blood pressure z-scores and high blood pressure.

362 No study has evaluated the association of urban green and blue spaces on metabolic syndrome in the
363 paediatric population. The metabolic syndrome is a cluster of conditions that occur together, namely, excess
364 body fat around the waist, high blood pressure, dyslipidemia, and hyperglycemia. Previous evidence on the
365 association of green and blue space exposure with metabolic outcomes during childhood is limited and has
366 shown mixed results. Inverse associations were observed between time spent in green spaces and glucose⁶⁷,
367 percentage of parkland and blue space and LDL cholesterol⁶⁸ and accessibility to green spaces and allostatic
368 load, which includes HDL cholesterol, blood pressure and glucose in its definition⁶⁹, while no associations
369 were observed between green space exposure and insulin resistance (HOMA-IR)⁷⁰. In the present study, after
370 correction for multiple testing, no significant association was observed between the exposure to blue and
371 green spaces and metabolic syndrome or its components. However, in the present study, after correction for
372 multiple testing, no significant association was observed between the exposure to blue and green spaces and
373 metabolic syndrome or its components.

374 Cardiometabolic conditions are complex and result from a web of risk versus protective factors. Our findings
375 suggest that urban natural spaces may not play a role in its development. Additionally, despite our life-course
376 approach from birth to late childhood, we did not find neither any specific period during childhood where
377 vulnerability to the effects of green and blue space exposure was particularly pronounced nor any cumulative
378 effect over time. Green and blue spaces have been associated with salutogenic effects, particularly related to
379 their utility in the development of health-promoting behaviours. These spaces might allow greater
380 opportunities for recreational physical activity and walkability, social contacts and community engagement,
381 reduction of stressors exposure, and cognitive and psychological restoration.² Despite the theoretical
382 framework, the effect of urban natural spaces by itself may not be sufficient to exert an impact on
383 cardiometabolic health in children. This aligns with previous literature, which suggests that urban green and
384 blue spaces have a stronger impact on mental health and psychological outcomes⁷¹ than on physical health.⁷²
385 We cannot disregard some methodological particularities of our study that might have precluded us from

386 finding significant associations. We considered blue spaces as only larger water bodies, such as rivers and
387 seas, thereby overlooking the potential positive impacts of smaller water bodies like fountains, ponds, and
388 lakes.⁷³ While we used two measures to assess green space exposure, only one measure was employed for
389 blue space exposure, which relied on cartographic data. The Normalized Difference Water Index (NDWI)
390 has been used for mapping and analyzing surface water.⁷⁴ Combining NDVI and NDWI enhances the contrast
391 between water bodies and surrounding surface features, significantly improving surface water detection,
392 particularly in mixed landscapes like urban and semi-urban environments where both vegetation and water
393 coexist.⁷⁴ However, in this study, we did not have the data on NDWI. Given the characteristics of the main
394 water bodies in the region of interest (ocean and river), we believe its inclusion would not substantially affect
395 our conclusions. Furthermore, we had information on greenness and residential proximity to the nearest green
396 spaces rather than utilization, which might be influenced by additional factors such as accessibility,
397 infrastructure, and safety.⁷⁵ Children are often exposed to green and blue spaces simultaneously and exploring
398 these exposures combined could further enrich our understanding of how natural environments influence
399 health outcomes. However, in this study, we were not able to address this, mainly due to sample size
400 constraints in combining trajectories and computational issues of more complex advanced models. We have
401 included both movers and non-movers in the analysis. This approach allowed us to capture changes in
402 exposure resulting from relocation or changes in the surrounding environment. It has been shown that the
403 impact of green spaces on health differs across socioeconomic groups and that they are differently distributed
404 according to neighbourhood socioeconomic characteristics.^{76,77} For instance, green spaces are frequently
405 lacking in the most economically disadvantaged neighbourhoods.^{76,78} A study conducted in Porto
406 municipality revealed that in socially deprived neighbourhoods, green spaces often have more safety issues,
407 signs of damage, insufficient recreational equipment, as well as fewer amenities like seating, restrooms, and
408 cafes⁷⁶, potentially making them less appealing to children and their families. In this study, there was no
409 interaction with maternal education and neighbourhood deprivation index, but we cannot disregard that these
410 variables, used as a proxy for socioeconomic position, may have been insufficient to depict the nature of
411 potential differences in socioeconomic characteristics over time.⁷⁹ Also, this study focuses on residential

412 urban green and blue space exposures, and thus, it might have been affected by the Uncertain Geographic
413 Context Problem since focusing on residential neighbourhoods does not account for the time that individuals
414 spend outside their home environment.⁸⁰ For instance, we did not account for the fact that school-aged
415 children, primarily from primary education onwards, spend at least eight hours per day at school or engage
416 in related activities from Monday to Friday. Therefore, the urban green and blue spaces surrounding school
417 environments may play a more significant role. Indeed, an inverse association between accessibility to green
418 spaces near schools and allostatic load, which includes, among other parameters, HDL, glucose, DBP and
419 SBP in its definition, was observed in seven-year-old children from G21.⁶⁹ We were not able to further
420 explore this in our study since we do not have information on NDVI or blue spaces around schools at any
421 time point and distance to the nearest green space is only available at 7 years. One could argue that the choice
422 of multiple testing corrections was overly conservative, which may explain why no significant associations
423 were found. Indeed, for metabolic outcomes, there were associations before the correction for multiple
424 testing, yet they were of low magnitude and lacked consistency across time points and between trajectories.
425 This prevented us from identifying any specific childhood period where vulnerability to green and blue space
426 exposure was particularly pronounced, despite our life-course approach from birth to late childhood.

427 This study has strengths worth acknowledging. The use of data from a large population-based birth
428 cohort study enabled the systematic collection of data throughout time. Additionally, the prevalence of
429 overweight/obesity, high blood pressure, and metabolic syndrome in our sample was higher than the
430 prevalence reported in childhood worldwide¹²⁻¹⁴, assuring a robust sample to explore the tested associations.
431 The combination of both blue and green spaces, along with two different measures to assess green space –
432 greenness (NDVI) and residential distance to the nearest green space - offer a more comprehensive approach
433 for analysing these features within the built environment. For greenness, we used different buffer sizes of
434 NDVI to capture various dimensions of exposure. For instance, a larger buffer size (500m) might include
435 commuting spaces and spaces where children spend their time⁸¹, while smaller buffer sizes (250m and 100m)
436 may reflect the exposure immediately surrounding children's residences.¹⁰ Also, the availability of these data
437 from birth until late childhood allowed us to employ a longitudinal approach, assessing their association with

438 cardiometabolic outcomes per follow-up and as life-course trajectories, as opposed to adding to most previous
439 evidence from cross-sectional studies. Moreover, we used detailed cardiometabolic health outcomes, which
440 were defined using robust data coming from anthropometric and blood pressure measurements as well as
441 from imaging techniques and fasting blood samples conducted by trained healthcare professionals following
442 standardized procedures.

443 However, this study has some limitations. We lacked data to assess the use of green and blue spaces by
444 children enrolled in the G21 cohort. In our study, the exclusion of participants with missing data on both
445 exposure and outcome measures may have introduced selection bias. When comparing excluded versus
446 included participants, we observed that among the excluded, 58% had mothers with a lower educational level
447 (vs 42.6% included) and 25% lived in the most deprived areas classified in the 5th quintile of the
448 neighbourhood deprivation index (vs 17%). Thus, our sample might not truly represent the socioeconomic
449 characteristics of the initial cohort participants. Furthermore, we are aware that relocation might also imply
450 changes in the confounding structure of these associations. However, in this study, restricting the analyses to
451 non-movers would substantially limit the variability in these exposures over time, and preclude the
452 development of meaningful trajectories. We have not included data on individual lifestyle choices, such as
453 physical activity and diet, as these variables are potential mediators in the causal pathway of the studied
454 associations and thus, their inclusion in traditional regression models could have led to biased estimates.^{82,83}
455 Also, no mediation analyses were conducted for individual lifestyle choices or other environmental hazards
456 since no significant association between blue and green space exposure and childhood cardiometabolic health
457 outcomes was observed in this study. Moreover, we did not have data on other potential confounders, such
458 as noise pollution, which could also impact our results through residual confounding.

459 In conclusion, this study did not find consistent associations between urban green and blue spaces
460 over key developmental periods and body mass index, body fat content and distribution, blood pressure, and
461 metabolic outcomes in childhood. It advances environmental health science by employing a robust
462 longitudinal methodology and highlights the need for more nuanced research approaches that account for

463 space usage patterns, environmental quality, and socioeconomic contexts when investigating environmental
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486 **Author contributions:**

487 BV was responsible for data analysis and interpretation and for drafting the manuscript. BA was responsible
488 for data analysis and interpretation. RP was responsible for drafting the manuscript and revision. AIR was

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492 of the manuscript for intellectual content and final approval of the version to be published. All authors
493 approved the final manuscript as submitted and agreed to be accountable for all aspects of the work.

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506

507 **Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process**

508 During the preparation of this work, the authors used ChatGPT OpenAI to improve language and
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511

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Table 1. Description of green and blue spaces exposures over childhood (n=4669)

	At birth	4 years	7 years	10 years
NDVI 100m , mean \pm SD	0.16 \pm 0.08	0.18 \pm 0.07	0.21 \pm 0.06	0.21 \pm 0.06
NDVI 250m , mean \pm SD	0.20 \pm 0.07	0.22 \pm 0.07	0.23 \pm 0.06	0.24 \pm 0.06
NDVI 500m , mean \pm SD	0.22 \pm 0.07	0.24 \pm 0.07	0.24 \pm 0.06	0.25 \pm 0.06
Distance to nearest green space (hm) , median (p25, p75)	9.24 (4.94, 15.07)	9.47 (5.06, 15.07)	9.49 (5.10, 15.14)	9.53 (5.15, 15.19)
Distance to nearest blue space (hm) , median (p25, p75)	18.43 (10.44, 29.99)	18.65 (10.68, 30.39)	18.73 (10.69, 30.50)	18.85 (10.78, 30.39)

Abbreviations: NDVI, normalized difference vegetation index; SD, standard deviation; hm, hectometre; p25-p75, 25th and 75th percentiles

Table 2. Participants' characteristics

	Total (n=4669)
At birth	
Sex, n (%)	
Female	2283 (48.9)
Male	2386 (51.1)
Maternal educational level, n (%)	
Low	1988 (42.6)
Medium	1321 (28.3)
High	1360 (29.1)
NO ₂ , mean ± SD	38.8 ± 8.4
PM2.5., median (p25, p75)	21.8 (21.1, 22.5)
Neighbourhood socioeconomic deprivation index, n (%)	
1 st quintile	643 (13.8)
2 nd quintile	1005 (21.5)
3 rd quintile	1186 (25.4)
4 th quintile	1029 (22.0)
5 th quintile	806 (17.3)
At 4 years	
NO ₂ , mean ± SD	30.2 ± 6.6
PM2.5., median (p25, p75)	14.5 (14.0, 15.0)
Neighbourhood socioeconomic deprivation index, n (%)	
1 st quintile	658 (14.1)
2 nd quintile	1029 (22.0)
3 rd quintile	1170 (25.1)
4 th quintile	1042 (22.3)
5 th quintile	770 (16.5)
At 7 years	
NO ₂ , mean ± SD	27.3 ± 6.0
PM2.5., median (p25, p75)	13.8 (13.2, 14.4)
Neighbourhood socioeconomic deprivation index, n (%)	
1 st quintile	649 (13.9)

2 nd quintile	1054 (22.6)
3 rd quintile	1164 (24.9)
4 th quintile	1046 (22.4)
5 th quintile	756 (16.2)
At 10 years	
BMI (kg/m ²), median (p25, p75)	18.2 (16.3, 20.9)
BMI z-scores, median (p25, p75)	0.7 (-0.2, 1.7)
Body weight status	
Normal weight	2616 (56.6)
Overweight/obesity	2002 (43.4)
Fat mass index (kg/m ⁴), median (p25, p75)	3.5 (2.7, 4.8)
Android-to-gynoid fat ratio, median (p25, p75)	0.8 (0.7, 0.9)
Systolic BP (mm/Hg), median (p25, p75)	108.0 (102.0, 114.0)
Systolic BP z-score, median (p25, p75)	0.5 (-0.0, 1.1)
Diastolic BP (mm/Hg), median (p25, p75)	69.0 (64.0, 74.0)
Diastolic BP z-score, median (p25, p75)	0.7 (0.3, 1.1)
Blood Pressure	
Normal blood pressure	3424 (73.5)
High blood pressure	1234 (26.5)
Metabolic outcomes	
Waist circumference (cm), median (p25, p75)	66.0 (60.5, 74.2)
Waist circumference z-score, median (p25, p75)	1.4 (0.4, 2.4)
Glucose (mg/dl), median (p25, p75)	87.0 (83.0, 91.0)
Glucose z-score, median (p25, p75)	-0.3 (-0.8, 0.2)
Insulin (mU/L), median (p25, p75)	8.0 (5.5, 11.7)
Insulin z-score, median (p25, p75)	0.6 (-0.3, 1.5)
Triglycerides (mg/dl), median (p25, p75)	60.0 (47.0, 79.0)
Triglycerides z-score, median (p25, p75)	0.6 (0.2, 1.1)
HDL cholesterol (mg/dl), median (p25, p75)	54.0 (48.0, 62.0)
HDL cholesterol z-score, median (p25, p75)	-0.1 (-0.6, 0.5)
HOMA-IR, median (p25, p75)	1.7 (1.1, 2.6)
HOMA-IR z-score, median (p25, p75)	0.5 (-0.4, 1.4)

Metabolic Syndrome Score, median (p25, p75)	2.6 (0.7, 4.7)
Metabolic Syndrome, n (%)	
No	2252 (82.5)
Yes	479 (17.5)
NO ₂ , mean ± SD	28.2 ± 6.1
PM2.5., median (p25, p75)	14.1 (13.7, 14.5)
Neighbourhood socioeconomic deprivation index, n (%)	
1 st quintile	660 (14.1)
2 nd quintile	1042 (22.3)
3 rd quintile	1159 (24.8)
4 th quintile	1031 (22.1)
5 th quintile	777 (16.6)

Abbreviations: BMI, body mass index; kg/m², kilogram per square metre; SD, standard deviation; p25-p75, 25th and 75th percentiles; NO₂, nitrogen dioxide; PM2.5., particulate matter less than 2.5 µm; BP, blood pressure; mmHg, millimetres of mercury; cm, centimetre; mg/dl, milligram per decilitre; mU/L, milliunit per litre

Table 3. Adjusted linear and logistic regression associations of green and blue spaces, at each time point, with continuous and dichotomic cardiometabolic outcomes at 10 years

		BMI z-scores (n=4666)	Overweight/ Obesity (n=4618)	Systolic blood pressure z-scores (n=4658)	Diastolic blood pressure z-scores (n=4658)	High blood pressure (n=4658)	Metabolic Syndrome Score (n=2731)	Metabolic Syndrome (n=2731)
		β [95% CI]	OR [95% CI]	β [95% CI]	β [95% CI]	OR [95% CI]	β [95% CI]	OR [95% CI]
At birth	NDVI 100m (SD)	-0.00 [-0.04;0.04]	0.97 [0.90;1.04]	0.02 [-0.01;0.05]	0.01 [-0.01;0.03]	1.05 [0.97; 1.13]	0.05 [-0.09;0.18]	0.99 [0.89; 1.10]
	NDVI 250m (SD)	-0.01 [-0.06;0.04]	0.94 [0.87; 1.01]	0.00 [-0.03;0.03]	0.01 [-0.01;0.03]	1.03 [0.94; 1.12]	-0.01 [-0.16;0.14]	0.97 [0.86; 1.09]
	NDVI 500m (SD)	-0.01 [-0.06;0.04]	0.94 [0.87; 1.02]	-0.01 [-0.05;0.02]	-0.01 [-0.04;0.01]	1.01 [0.92; 1.10]	-0.09 [-0.24;0.07]	1.00 [0.88; 1.14]
	Distance to nearest green space (SD)	0.01 [-0.03;0.05]	1.01 [0.95; 1.09]	0.02 [-0.00;0.04]	0.00 [-0.00;0.00]	1.06 [0.99; 1.14]	0.10 [-0.03;0.23]	0.98 [0.85; 1.13]
	Distance to nearest blue space (SD)	-0.00 [-0.04;0.04]	0.98 [0.92;1.04]	-0.02*† [-0.05; -0.00]	-0.01 [-0.03;0.01]	0.95 [0.89; 1.02]	-0.03 [-0.01;0.09]	1.09 [0.97; 1.22]
4 years	NDVI 100m (SD)	-0.01 [-0.06; 0.03]	0.96 [0.90; 1.03]	0.01 [-0.02;0.04]	0.01 [-0.02;0.03]	1.02 [0.94; 1.05]	0.05 [-0.08; 0.19]	0.99 [0.88; 1.12]
	NDVI 250m (SD)	-0.01 [-0.06;0.04]	0.97 [0.89; 1.05]	-0.02 [-0.05;0.01]	0.01 [-0.02;0.03]	0.99 [0.90; 1.07]	0.05 [-0.10;0.20]	1.00 [0.87; 1.14]
	NDVI 500m (SD)	-0.01 [-0.06;0.04]	0.98 [0.90; 1.06]	-0.03 [-0.06;0.01]	-0.01 [-0.03;0.02]	0.98 [0.89; 1.08]	-0.02 [-0.18;0.15]	0.97 [0.84; 1.13]
	Distance to nearest green space (SD)	0.03 [-0.01;0.07]	1.04 [0.98; 1.12]	0.00 [-0.02;0.03]	0.01 [-0.01;0.03]	1.02 [0.95; 1.10]	0.12 [-0.01; 0.25]	1.07 [0.95; 1.20]
	Distance to nearest blue space (SD)	-0.01 [-0.05;0.03]	0.98 [0.92; 1.04]	-0.02 [-0.04;0.01]	-0.01 [-0.02;0.01]	0.95 [0.89; 1.02]	-0.00 [-0.12;0.12]	1.01 [0.90; 1.12]
7 years	NDVI 100m (SD)	-0.01 [-0.05;0.04]	0.97 [0.90; 1.04]	0.00 [-0.03;0.03]	0.00 [-0.02;0.02]	1.02 [0.94; 1.10]	0.01 [-0.12;0.14]	0.98 [0.87; 1.10]
	NDVI 250m (SD)	-0.01 [-0.05;0.04]	0.96 [0.89; 1.04]	0.00 [-0.43;0.43]	0.01 [-0.01;0.04]	1.03 [0.94; 1.12]	0.04 [-0.11;0.18]	1.04 [0.91; 1.18]
	NDVI 500m (SD)	-0.01 [-0.06; 0.04]	0.96 [0.89; 1.04]	-0.02 [-0.05;0.02]	-0.00 [-0.03;0.02]	1.02 [0.93; 1.11]	-0.02 [-0.17;0.14]	1.00 [0.87; 1.15]
	Distance to nearest green space (SD)	0.04 [-0.00;0.07]	1.04 [0.97; 1.11]	0.01 [-0.02;0.03]	0.01 [-0.01;0.03]	1.04 [0.96; 1.12]	0.13*† [0.01;0.26]	1.07 [0.96; 1.20]
	Distance to nearest blue space (SD)	-0.01 [-0.05;0.03]	0.98 [0.92; 1.04]	-0.02 [-0.05;0.01]	-0.01 [-0.03;0.01]	0.95 [0.89; 1.02]	-0.03 [-0.14;0.09]	1.00 [0.90; 1.11]
10 years	NDVI 100m (SD)	-0.01 [-0.05;0.03]	0.98 [0.91; 1.05]	0.01 [-0.01; 0.04]	0.01 [-0.01;0.03]	1.03 [0.95; 1.11]	0.09 [-0.04;0.22]	1.03 [0.92; 1.16]
	NDVI 250m (SD)	-0.01 [-0.06;0.04]	0.96 [0.89; 1.04]	-0.01 [-0.04;0.03]	0.02 [-0.01;0.04]	1.02 [0.93; 1.11]	0.11 [-0.03;0.26]	1.07 [0.94; 1.22]
	NDVI 500m (SD)	-0.02 [-0.07;0.03]	0.97 [0.89; 1.06]	-0.01 [-0.05;0.02]	0.01 [-0.02;0.03]	1.01 [0.92; 1.11]	0.03 [-0.13;0.18]	1.02 [0.89; 1.18]
	Distance to nearest green space (SD)	0.04 [-0.00;0.08]	1.04 [0.97; 1.11]	0.00 [-0.02;0.03]	0.01 [-0.01;0.03]	1.03 [0.96; 1.11]	0.14*† [0.01;0.27]	1.07 [0.95; 1.20]
	Distance to nearest blue space (SD)	-0.00 [-0.04;0.04]	0.99 [0.94; 1.06]	-0.02 [-0.04;0.01]	-0.00 [-0.02;0.02]	0.96 [0.90; 1.03]	0.00 [-0.01;0.12]	1.02 [0.91; 1.13]

Abbreviations: BMI, body mass index; NDVI, normalized difference vegetation index; CI, confidence interval; SD, standard deviation. * p-value < 0.05; † Indicates loss of significance after multiple testing correction. β values are regression coefficients (95% confidence interval) from linear regression models, reflecting the change in body mass index z-score, systolic and diastolic blood pressure z-scores, and metabolic syndrome score at 10

years, per unit of increase of each standard deviation of exposure, at each follow-up. OR values are odds ratios (95% confidence interval) from logistic regression models, reflecting the odds of having overweight/obesity, high blood pressure, and metabolic syndrome at 10 years, per unit of increase of each standard deviation of exposure, at each follow-up. Adjusted β and OR consider maternal educational level at birth, and neighbourhood socioeconomic deprivation index, nitrogen dioxide (NO₂) and particulate matter less than 2.5 μ m (PM_{2.5}.) at each respective time point

Table 4. Adjusted linear and logistic regression associations of green and blue spaces trajectories with continuous and dichotomic cardiometabolic outcomes at 10 years

		BMI z-scores (n=4666)	Overweight/ Obesity (n=4618)	Systolic blood pressure z-scores (n=4658)	Diastolic blood pressure z-scores (n=4658)	High blood pressure (n=4658)	Metabolic Syndrome Score (n=2731)	Metabolic Syndrome (n=2731)
		β [95% CI]	OR [95% CI]	β [95% CI]	β [95% CI]	OR [95% CI]	β [95% CI]	OR [95% CI]
NDVI 100m	Low ascending	0.03 [-0.07;0.14]	1.12 [0.94; 1.33]	-0.00 [-0.08;0.07]	-0.02 [-0.07;0.04]	0.92 [0.76; 1.11]	-0.03 [-0.36;0.31]	0.96 [0.72; 1.30]
	High stable	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
NDVI 250m	Low ascending	0.02 [-0.17;0.21]	1.13 [0.96;1.34]	0.01 [-0.14; 0.16]	-0.00 [-0.05;0.05]	0.98 [0.64; 1.44]	0.04 [-0.27;0.35]	1.02 [0.77; 1.36]
	Descending	-0.03 [-0.25;0.18]	1.01 [0.70; 1.44]	0.04 [-0.03;0.11]	-0.08 [-0.18;0.03]	1.11 [0.92; 1.34]	-0.73 [-1.42;0.05]	0.64 [0.31; 1.23]
	Ascending	0.06 [-0.04;0.16]	1.20 [0.87; 1.65]	-0.01 [-0.14; 0.13]	-0.04 [-0.10;0.09]	1.14 [0.79; 1.62]	0.05 [-0.58;0.67]	0.92 [0.50; 1.62]
	High stable	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
NDVI 500m	Low ascending	0.01 [-0.09;0.11]	1.06 [0.90; 1.25]	0.01 [-0.01;0.16]	0.03 [-0.02;0.07]	1.04 [0.87; 1.25]	0.08 [-0.22;0.38]	1.07 [0.81; 1.40]
	Descending	-0.19 [-0.41;0.03]	0.84 [0.58; 1.21]	0.04 [-0.02;0.11]	-0.15* [†] [-0.26; -0.04]	0.84 [0.59; 1.20]	-0.72* [†] [-1.38; -0.07]	0.73 [0.38; 1.31]
	Ascending	0.02 [-0.16;0.20]	1.28 [0.94; 1.74]	-0.06 [-0.19;0.07]	-0.01 [-0.10;0.09]	0.82 [0.59; 1.20]	-0.09 [-0.07; 0.52]	0.60 [0.30; 1.12]
	High stable	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
Distance to nearest green space	Medium stable	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
	Descending	-0.01 [-0.28;0.14]	1.01 [0.71 1.43]	0.02 [-0.12;0.17]	-0.00 [-0.11;0.10]	1.01 [0.68; 1.47]	0.23 [-0.41;0.87]	1.09 [0.61; 1.85]
	Ascending	0.03 [-0.18;0.24]	1.02 [0.72; 1.45]	0.00 [-0.15;0.15]	0.04 [-0.07;0.14]	0.96 [0.63; 1.41]	-0.01 [-0.67; 0.65]	0.79 [0.39; 1.45]
Distance to nearest blue space	Low stable	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
	High stable	-0.06 [-0.18;0.05]	0.95 [0.79; 1.15]	-0.06 [-0.14; 0.02]	-0.02 [-0.07;0.04]	0.88 [0.72; 1.08]	-0.23 [-0.57;0.12]	0.92 [0.68;1.27]

Abbreviations: BMI, body mass index; NDVI, normalized difference vegetation index; CI, confidence interval. * p-value < 0.05; [†] Indicates loss of significance after multiple testing correction. β values are regression coefficients (95% confidence interval) from linear regression models, reflecting the change in body mass index z-score, systolic and diastolic blood pressure z-scores, and metabolic syndrome score at 10 years, for each trajectory as compared to the reference trajectory. OR values are odds ratios (95% confidence interval) from logistic regression models, reflecting the odds of having overweight/obesity, high blood pressure, and metabolic syndrome at 10 years, for each trajectory as compared to the reference trajectory. Adjusted β and OR consider maternal educational level at birth, and neighbourhood socioeconomic deprivation index, nitrogen dioxide (NO₂) and particulate matter less than 2.5 μm (PM_{2.5}) at birth and at 10 years.

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Figure 1. NDVI 100m, 250m and 500m, and residential distance to green and blue spaces, from birth to 10 years of age

Supplementary Data

Residential exposure to green and blue spaces over childhood and cardiometabolic health outcomes: The Generation XXI birth cohort

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Figure S1. Flowchart of the study population

Figure S2. Directed acyclic graph (DAG) to identify potential confounders of the association between residential green and blue spaces and child cardiometabolic health

Figure S3. Correlation matrix of the environmental exposures

Table S1. Description of green and blue space exposures over childhood in the sample used to derive trajectories (n=7549)

	At birth	4 years	7 years	10 years
NDVI 100m , mean \pm SD	0.16 \pm 0.08	0.18 \pm 0.07	0.21 \pm 0.06	0.21 \pm 0.06
NDVI 250m , mean \pm SD	0.20 \pm 0.08	0.21 \pm 0.07	0.23 \pm 0.06	0.23 \pm 0.06
NDVI 500m , mean \pm SD	0.22 \pm 0.07	0.23 \pm 0.07	0.24 \pm 0.06	0.25 \pm 0.06
Distance to nearest green space (hm) , median	9.30	9.54	9.60	9.62
(p25, p75)	(4.92, 14.90)	(5.02, 14.91)	(5.11, 14.95)	(5.15, 14.98)
Distance to nearest blue space (hm) , median (p25,	18.43	18.51	18.57	18.66
p75)	(10.27, 29.90)	(10.44, 30.24)	(10.44, 30.23)	(10.49, 30.10)

Abbreviations: NDVI, normalized difference vegetation index; SD, standard deviation; p25-p75, 25th and 75th percentiles

Table S2. Comparison between included and non-included participants

	Included (n=4669)	Non-included (n=3682)	p-value
Environmental exposures			
<i>At birth</i>			
NDVI 100m, mean ± SD	0.16 ± 0.08	0.16 ± 0.08	0.529
NDVI 250m, mean ± SD	0.20 ± 0.07	0.20 ± 0.08	0.031
NDVI 500m, mean ± SD	0.22 ± 0.07	0.22 ± 0.07	0.002
Distance to nearest green space (hm), median (p25, p75)	9.24 (4.94, 15.07)	9.09 (4.70, 14.64)	0.189
Distance to nearest blue space (hm), median (p25, p75)	18.43 (10.44, 29.99)	18.00 (9.36, 29.44)	0.018
<i>4 years</i>			
NDVI 100m, mean ± SD	0.18 ± 0.07	0.18 ± 0.07	0.991
NDVI 250m, mean ± SD	0.22 ± 0.07	0.21 ± 0.08	0.006
NDVI 500m, mean ± SD	0.24 ± 0.07	0.23 ± 0.07	<0.001
Distance to nearest green space (hm), median (p25, p75)	9.47 (5.06, 15.07)	9.53 (4.88, 14.68)	0.326
Distance to nearest blue space (hm), median (p25, p75)	18.65 (10.68, 30.39)	17.98 (9.37, 29.37)	0.005
<i>7 years</i>			
NDVI 100m, mean ± SD	0.21 ± 0.06	0.20 ± 0.06	0.010
NDVI 250m, mean ± SD	0.23 ± 0.06	0.23 ± 0.06	<0.001
NDVI 500m, mean ± SD	0.24 ± 0.06	0.24 ± 0.06	<0.001
Distance to nearest green space (hm), median (p25, p75)	9.49 (5.10, 15.14)	9.56 (4.98, 14.62)	0.396
Distance to nearest blue space (hm), median (p25, p75)	18.73 (10.69, 30.50)	17.97 (9.39, 29.19)	0.002
<i>10 years</i>			
NDVI 100m, mean ± SD	0.21 ± 0.06	0.21 ± 0.06	0.038
NDVI 250m, mean ± SD	0.24 ± 0.06	0.23 ± 0.06	0.005
NDVI 500m, mean ± SD	0.25 ± 0.06	0.24 ± 0.06	<0.001
Distance to nearest green space (hm), median (p25, p75)	9.53 (5.15, 15.19)	9.56 (4.99, 14.69)	0.395
Distance to nearest blue space (hm), median (p25, p75)	18.85 (10.78, 30.39)	17.97 (9.37, 29.31)	0.001
Participant characteristics			
<i>At birth</i>			
Sex			
Female	2283 (48.9)	1803 (49.0)	0.966
Male	2386 (51.1)	1879 (51.0)	
Maternal characteristics			
Maternal educational level, n (%)			
Low	1988 (42.6)	2111 (58.2)	<0.001
Medium	1321 (28.3)	897 (24.7)	
High	1360 (29.1)	618 (17.0)	

Environmental characteristics*At birth*

NO ₂ , mean ± SD	38.8 ± 8.4	37.5 ± 9.9	<0.001
PM2.5, median (p25, p75)	21.8 (21.1, 22.5)	21.6 (20.6, 22.4)	<0.001
Neighbourhood socioeconomic deprivation index, n (%)			
1 st quintile	643 (13.8)	404 (11.1)	
2 nd quintile	1005 (21.5)	621 (17.0)	
3 rd quintile	1186 (25.4)	871 (23.9)	<0.001
4 th quintile	1029 (22.0)	829 (22.7)	
5 th quintile	806 (17.3)	924 (25.3)	

4 years

NO ₂ , mean ± SD	30.2 ± 6.6	28.8 ± 7.8	<0.001
PM2.5, median (p25, p75)	14.5 (14.0, 15.0)	14.4 (13.6, 15.0)	<0.001
Neighbourhood socioeconomic deprivation index, n (%)			
1 st quintile	658 (14.1)	413 (11.3)	
2 nd quintile	1029 (22.0)	619 (17.0)	
3 rd quintile	1170 (25.1)	864 (23.7)	<0.001
4 th quintile	1042 (22.3)	864 (23.7)	
5 th quintile	770 (16.5)	891 (24.4)	

7 years

NO ₂ , mean ± SD	27.3 ± 6.0	26.1 ± 7.1	<0.001
PM2.5, median (p25, p75)	13.8 (13.2, 14.4)	13.6 (12.8, 14.3)	<0.001
Neighbourhood socioeconomic deprivation index, n (%)			
1 st quintile	649 (13.9)	422 (11.6)	
2 nd quintile	1054 (22.6)	627 (17.2)	
3 rd quintile	1164 (24.9)	859 (23.5)	<0.001
4 th quintile	1046 (22.4)	860 (23.6)	
5 th quintile	756 (16.2)	881 (24.1)	

10 years

NO ₂ , mean ± SD	28.2 ± 6.1	26.8 ± 7.4	<0.001
PM2.5, median (p25, p75)	14.1 (13.7, 14.5)	13.9 (13.1, 14.4)	<0.001
Neighbourhood socioeconomic deprivation index, n (%)			
1 st quintile	660 (14.1)	428 (11.7)	
2 nd quintile	1042 (22.3)	633 (17.4)	
3 rd quintile	1159 (24.8)	871 (23.9)	<0.001
4 th quintile	1031 (22.1)	844 (23.1)	
5 th quintile	777 (16.6)	870 (23.9)	

Abbreviations: NDVI, Normalized Difference Vegetation Index; hm, hectometre; SD, standard deviation; p25, p75, 25th and 75th percentiles; NO₂, nitrogen dioxide; PM2.5, particulate matter less than 2.5 µm

Table S3. Crude linear and logistic regression associations between green and blue spaces, at each time point, with continuous and dichotomic cardiometabolic outcomes at 10 years

	BMI z-scores (n=4666)	Overweight/ Obesity (n=4618)	Systolic blood pressure z-scores (n=4658)	Diastolic blood pressure z-scores (n=4658)	High blood pressure (n=4658)	Metabolic Syndrome Score (n=2731)	Metabolic Syndrome (n=2731)	
	β [CI 95%]	OR [CI 95%]	β [CI 95%]	β [CI 95%]	OR [CI 95%]	β [CI 95%]	OR [CI 95%]	
At birth	NDVI 100m (SD)	0.03 [-0.00; 0.07]	1.02 [0.96; 1.08]	0.03* [0.01; 0.06]	0.02 [-0.00; 0.03]	1.07 [1.00; 1.14]	0.12* [0.00; 0.23]	1.00 [0.90; 1.08]
	NDVI 250 m (SD)	0.04* [0.00; 0.08]	1.02 [0.96; 1.08]	0.02 [-0.01; 0.04]	0.02 [-0.00; 0.03]	1.05 [0.98; 1.12]	0.09 [-0.02; 0.20]	1.03 [0.93; 1.13]
	NDVI 500m (SD)	0.04* [0.01; 0.08]	1.02 [0.96; 1.08]	0.01 [-0.02; 0.03]	0.01 [-0.01; 0.02]	1.03 [0.97; 1.10]	0.05 [-0.06; 0.16]	1.01 [0.92; 1.12]
	Distance to nearest green space (SD)	0.04* [0.01; 0.08]	1.05 [0.99; 1.12]	0.02 [-0.00; 0.05]	0.02 [0.00; 0.04]	1.07 [1.00; 1.15]	0.17* [0.05; 0.29]	1.10 [1.00; 1.12]
	Distance to nearest blue space (SD)	0.00 [-0.03; 0.04]	0.98 [0.93; 1.04]	-0.02 [-0.05; 0.00]	-0.01 [-0.03; 0.01]	0.95 [0.89; 1.02]	-0.01 [-0.12; 0.11]	0.99 [0.89; 1.09]
	4 years	NDVI 100m (SD)	0.02 [-0.01; 0.06]	1.00 [0.94; 1.06]	0.02 [-0.00; 0.05]	0.01 [-0.01; 0.03]	1.05 [0.98; 1.12]	0.12* [0.01; 0.23]
NDVI 250 m (SD)		0.03 [-0.00; 0.07]	1.02 [0.96; 1.08]	0.00 [-0.02; 0.03]	0.02 [-0.00; 0.03]	1.03 [0.97; 1.10]	0.11* [0.00; 0.23]	1.01 [0.92; 1.12]
NDVI 500m (SD)		0.04* [0.00; 0.07]	1.03 [0.97; 1.09]	-0.00 [-0.03; 0.03]	0.01 [-0.01; 0.03]	1.03 [0.96; 1.10]	0.08 [-0.03; 0.19]	1.00 [0.90; 1.10]
Distance to nearest green space (SD)		0.05* [0.02; 0.09]	1.06 [1.00; 1.13]	0.02 [-0.01; 0.04]	0.01 [-0.00; 0.03]	1.05 [0.98; 1.10]	0.18 [0.07; 0.30]	1.08 [0.98; 1.19]
Distance to nearest blue space (SD)		-0.00 [-0.04; 0.03]	0.99 [0.93; 1.05]	-0.02 [-0.05; 0.01]	-0.01 [-0.02; 0.01]	0.95 [0.89; 1.02]	0.01 [-0.11; 0.12]	0.99 [0.90; 1.10]
7 years		NDVI 100m (SD)	0.02 [-0.01; 0.06]	1.01 [0.95; 1.07]	0.02 [-0.01; 0.04]	0.01 [-0.01; 0.03]	1.04 [0.98; 1.12]	0.09 [-0.02; 0.20]
	NDVI 250 m (SD)	0.03 [-0.00; 0.07]	1.01 [0.96; 1.08]	0.01 [-0.01; 0.04]	0.02 [-0.00; 0.04]	1.05 [0.99; 1.12]	0.12* [0.00; 0.23]	1.03 [0.94; 1.14]
	NDVI 500m (SD)	0.03 [-0.00; 0.07]	1.02 [0.96; 1.08]	0.01 [-0.02; 0.03]	0.01 [-0.01; 0.03]	1.04 [0.97; 1.11]	0.08 [-0.03; 0.19]	1.01 [0.91; 1.11]
	Distance to nearest green space (SD)	0.06* [0.02; 0.09]	1.06 [1.00; 1.12]	0.02 [-0.01; 0.04]	0.01 [-0.00; 0.03]	1.05 [0.99; 1.12]	0.20* [0.08; 0.31]	1.09 [0.98; 1.20]
	Distance to nearest blue space (SD)	-0.00 [-0.04; 0.03]	0.99 [0.93; 1.05]	-0.02 [-0.04; 0.01]	-0.01 [-0.03; 0.01]	0.95 [0.89; 1.02]	-0.01 [-0.13; 0.10]	0.99 [0.89; 1.09]
	10 years	NDVI 100m (SD)	0.03 [-0.01; 0.06]	1.01 [0.95; 1.06]	0.02 [-0.01; 0.04]	0.01 [-0.01; 0.03]	1.03 [0.96; 1.09]	0.12* [0.00; 0.23]
NDVI 250 m (SD)		0.03 [-0.00; 0.07]	1.01 [0.96; 1.08]	0.01 [-0.02; 0.03]	0.01 [-0.00; 0.03]	1.02 [0.96; 1.09]	0.13* [0.01; 0.24]	1.03 [0.93; 1.13]
NDVI 500m (SD)		0.03 [-0.01; 0.06]	1.02 [0.96; 1.08]	0.01 [-0.02; 0.03]	0.01 [-0.01; 0.03]	1.02 [0.95; 1.09]	0.07 [-0.04; 0.18]	1.00 [0.90; 1.10]
Distance to nearest green space (SD)		0.06* [0.03; 0.10]	1.06 [1.00; 1.12]	0.01 [-0.01; 0.04]	0.01 [-0.01; 0.03]	1.03 [0.97; 1.10]	0.18* [0.06; 0.30]	1.06 [0.96; 1.17]
Distance to nearest blue space (SD)		0.01 [-0.03; 0.04]	1.00 [0.95; 1.06]	-0.01 [-0.04; 0.01]	-0.00 [-0.02; 0.01]	0.96 [0.89; 1.02]	0.01 [-0.10; 0.13]	1.00 [0.90; 1.11]

Abbreviations: BMI, body mass index; NDVI, normalized difference vegetation index; CI, confidence interval; SD, standard deviation * p-value < 0.05; β values are regression coefficients (95% confidence interval) from linear regression models, reflecting the change in body mass index z-score, systolic and diastolic blood pressure z-scores, and metabolic syndrome score, per unit of increase of each standard deviation of exposure, at each follow-up. OR values are odds ratios

(95% confidence interval) from logistic regression models, reflecting the odds of having overweight/obesity, high blood pressure, and metabolic syndrome at 10 years, per unit of increase of each standard deviation of exposure, at each follow-up

Table S4. Crude and adjusted linear regression associations of green and blue spaces, at each time point, with continuous body fat content and fat distribution outcomes at 10 years (n=2623)

	Fat mass index		Android-to-gynoid fat ratio		
	Crude model Exp(β) [95% CI]	Adjusted model Exp(β) [95% CI]	Crude model β [95% CI]	Adjusted model β [95% CI]	
At birth	NDVI 100m (SD)	1.02 [1.01;1.04]	1.02 [1.00;1.03]	0.01 [0.00;0.01]	0.01 [0.00;0.01]
	NDVI 250 m (SD)	1.02 [1.00; 1.03]	1.01 [0.99;1.03]	0.01 [0.00; 0.01]	0.00 [-0.00;0.01]
	NDVI 500m (SD)	1.02 [1.00; 1.03]	1.01 [0.99;1.03]	0.01 [0.00;0.01]	-0.02 [-0.00;0.02]
	Distance to nearest green space (SD)	1.01 [1.00; 1.03]	1.00 [0.99;1.02]	0.00 [-0.00;0.01]	0.00 [-0.01;0.01]
	Distance to nearest blue space (SD)	0.99 [0.98; 1.01]	0.99 [0.97;1.00]	-0.00 [-0.01;0.00]	-0.00 [-0.01;0.00]
	4 years	NDVI 100m (SD)	1.01 [1.00; 1.03]	1.01 [0.99;1.02]	0.00 [-0.00; 0.01]
NDVI 250 m (SD)		1.01 [1.00; 1.03]	1.00 [0.98;1.02]	0.00 [-0.00; 0.01]	0.00 [-0.00;0.01]
NDVI 500m (SD)		1.01 [1.00; 1.03]	1.00 [0.98;1.02]	0.00 [-0.00; 0.01]	0.00 [-0.00;0.01]
Distance to nearest green space (SD)		1.01 [1.00;1.03]	1.00 [0.99;1.02]	0.00 [-0.00; 0.01]	0.00 [-0.01;0.01]
Distance to nearest blue space (SD)		0.99 [0.97;1.00]	0.98 [0.97;1.00]	-0.00 [-0.01; 0.01]	-0.00 [-0.01;0.01]
7 years		NDVI 100m (SD)	1.01 [1.00; 1.03]	1.01 [0.90;1.02]	0.00 [-0.00; 0.01]
	NDVI 250 m (SD)	1.01 [1.00; 1.03]	1.01 [1.00;1.08]	0.01 [-0.00; 0.01]	0.00 [-0.00;0.01]
	NDVI 500m (SD)	1.01 [1.00; 1.02]	1.00 [0.98;1.02]	0.01 [-0.00; 0.01]	0.00 [-0.00;0.01]
	Distance to nearest green space (SD)	1.01 [1.00; 1.03]	1.01 [0.99;1.02]	0.00 [-0.00; 0.01]	0.00 [-0.00;0.01]
	Distance to nearest blue space (SD)	0.99 [0.97; 1.00]	0.98 [0.97;1.00]	-0.00 [-0.01;0.00]	-0.00 [-0.01;0.00]
	10 years	NDVI 100m (SD)	1.01 [0.99; 1.02]	1.00 [0.98;1.02]	0.00 [-0.00; 0.01]
NDVI 250 m (SD)		1.00 [0.99; 1.02]	1.00 [0.98;1.01]	0.00 [-0.00; 0.01]	-0.00 [-0.01;0.01]
NDVI 500m (SD)		1.00 [0.99; 1.02]	0.99 [0.97;1.01]	0.00 [-0.00; 0.01]	0.00 [-0.01;0.01]
Distance to nearest green space (SD)		1.01 [0.99; 1.02]	1.00 [0.99;1.02]	0.00 [-0.00; 0.01]	0.00 [-0.01;0.01]
Distance to nearest blue space (SD)		0.99 [0.98; 1.01]	0.99 [0.97;1.00]	0.00 [-0.01;0.01]	-0.00 [-0.01;0.01]

Abbreviations: NDVI, normalized difference vegetation index; CI, confidence interval; SD, standard deviation. β and Exponential (Exp) β values are regression coefficients and their exponentiation (95% confidence interval) from linear regression models, reflecting the absolute change in android-to-gynoid fat ratio and the relative change in fat mass index, respectively, per unit of increase of each standard deviation of exposure, at each follow-up. Adjusted β and exp(β) consider maternal educational level at birth, and neighbourhood deprivation index, nitrogen dioxide (NO₂) and particulate matter less than 2.5 μ m (PM2.5) at each respective time point

Table S5. Criteria to assess model fit for latent group analysis model for Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) and distance to the nearest green and blue space

	Number of groups			
	1	2	3	4
NDVI 100m				
<i>AIC</i>	-102880.1	-103636.2	-103628.2	-103620.2
<i>BIC</i>	-102810.8	-103539.2	-103503.5	-103467.8
NDVI 250m				
<i>AIC</i>	-109390.3	-109602.3	-110668.3	-112102.2
<i>BIC</i>	-109321.0	-109519.1	-110543.6	-111949.7
NDVI 500m				
<i>AIC</i>	-115646.1	-116213.4	-117141.8	-118397.6
<i>BIC</i>	-115576.8	-116116.4	-117017.1	-118245.2
Distance to the nearest green space (hm)				
<i>AIC</i>	38846.9	37239.1	33850.5	33858.4
<i>BIC</i>	38916.2	37336.1	33975.2	34011.0
Distance to the nearest blue space (hm)				
<i>AIC</i>	33959.7	33280.8	33224.9	33296.8
<i>BIC</i>	34028.9	33377.9	33349.6	33449.3

Abbreviations: NDVI, normalized difference vegetation index; AIC, Akaike Information Criterion; BIC, Bayesian Information Criterion; hm, hectometre

Table S6. Probability of belonging to each latent class for Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) and distance to the nearest green and blue space

	Number of groups			
	1	2	3	4
NDVI 100m				
<i>Probability 1</i>	0.8325	0.0528		
<i>Probability 2</i>	0.1675	0.9472		
NDVI 250m				
<i>Probability 1</i>	0.8981	0.0061	0.0024	0.0000
<i>Probability 2</i>	0.0874	0.9186	0.1596	0.0660
<i>Probability 3</i>	0.0145	0.0719	0.8315	0.0425
<i>Probability 4</i>	0.0000	0.0033	0.0064	0.8915
NDVI 500m				
<i>Probability 1</i>	0.8981	0.0000	0.0076	0.0028
<i>Probability 2</i>	0.0000	0.9028	0.0024	0.0052
<i>Probability 3</i>	0.0809	0.0484	0.9093	0.1378
<i>Probability 4</i>	0.0211	0.0488	0.0806	0.8542
Distance to the nearest green space (hm)				
<i>Probability 1</i>	0.9976	0.0504	0.0368	
<i>Probability 2</i>	0.0015	0.9496	0.0000	
<i>Probability 3</i>	0.0010	0.0000	0.9632	
Distance to the nearest blue space (hm)				
<i>Probability 1</i>	0.9558	0.1692		
<i>Probability 2</i>	0.0442	0.8308		

Abbreviations: NDVI, normalized difference vegetation index; hm, hectometre

Table S7. Description of the natural spaces exposure trajectories

	Trajectories	Sample used for deriving trajectories (n=7549) n (%)	Study sample (n=4669) n (%)
NDVI 100m	Low ascending	6334 (83.9)	3922 (84.0)
	High stable (ref)	1215 (16.1)	747 (16.0)
NDVI 250m	Low ascending	5248 (69.5)	3223 (69.0)
	Descending	233 (3.1)	148 (3.2)
	Ascending	298 (3.9)	207 (4.4)
	High stable (ref)	1770 (23.4)	1091 (23.4)
NDVI 500m	Low ascending	4914 (65.1)	3007 (64.4)
	Descending	216 (2.9)	148 (3.2)
	Ascending	332 (4.4)	227 (4.9)
	High stable (ref)	2087 (27.6)	1287 (27.6)
Distance to nearest green space	Medium stable (ref)	7215 (95.6)	4396 (94.2)
	Descending	161 (2.1)	136 (2.9)
	Ascending	173 (2.3)	137 (2.9)
Distance to nearest blue space	Low stable (ref)	861 (11.4)	528 (11.3)
	High stable	6688 (88.6)	4141 (88.7)

Abbreviations: NDVI, normalized difference vegetation index

Table S8. Crude linear and logistic regression associations between green and blue spaces trajectories with continuous and dichotomic cardiometabolic outcomes at 10 years

		BMI z-scores (n=4666)	Overweight/ Obesity (n=4618)	Systolic blood pressure z-scores (n=4658)	Diastolic blood pressure z-scores (n=4658)	High blood pressure (n=4658)	Metabolic Syndrome Score (n=2731)	Metabolic Syndrome (n=2731)
		β [CI 95%]	OR [95% CI]	β [CI 95%]	β [CI 95%]	OR [95% CI]	β [CI 95%]	OR [95% CI]
NDVI 100m	Low ascending	-0.05 [-0.14;0.05]	1.00 [0.86; 1.18]	-0.04 [-0.11; -0.03]	-0.030 [-0.078; 0.018]	0.87 [0.73; 1.04]	-0.21 [-0.51; 0.10]	0.92 [0.71; 1.21]
	High stable	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
NDVI 250m	Low ascending	-0.05 [-0.13;0.04]	0.99 [0.86; 1.14]	-0.01 [-0.07; 0.05]	-0.021 [-0.063; 0.021]	1.01 [0.86; 1.18]	-0.15 [-0.41; 0.12]	0.98 [0.78; 1.24]
	Descending	-0.11 [-0.32;0.11]	0.92 [0.64; 1.30]	-0.02 [-0.16; 0.13]	-0.077 [-0.182; 0.028]	0.96 [0.64; 1.41]	-0.76* [-1.44; -0.09]	0.69 [0.34; 1.30]
	Ascending	-0.08 [-0.26;0.11]	1.01 [0.75; 1.37]	-0.05 [-0.18; 0.07]	-0.044 [-0.135; 0.047]	0.98 [0.70; 1.37]	-0.18 [-0.77; 0.41]	0.82 [0.46; 1.40]
	High stable	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
	Low ascending	-0.09 [-0.17; -0.01]	0.94 [0.82; 1.07]	0.00 [-0.06; 0.06]	-0.004 [-0.044; 0.036]	0.97 [0.84; 1.13]	-0.12 [-0.37; 0.13]	1.00 [0.80; 1.25]
NDVI 500m	Descending	-0.23* [-0.43; -0.02]	0.84 [0.59; 1.18]	-0.02 [-0.16; 0.13]	-0.143* [-0.247; -0.039]	0.83 [0.55; 1.22]	-0.73* [-1.35; -0.09]	0.67 [0.34; 1.21]
	Ascending	-0.09 [-0.26;0.09]	1.07 [0.80; 1.42]	-0.10 [-0.23; 0.02]	-0.055 [-0.141; 0.032]	0.76 [0.54; 1.05]	-0.38 [-0.96; 0.19]	0.63 [0.33; 1.09]
	High stable	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
	Medium stable	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
Distance to nearest green space	Descending	-0.05 [-0.26;0.16]	1.08 [0.76; 1.52]	0.02 [-0.13; 0.16]	0.013 [-0.091;0.118]	1.08 [0.73; 1.56]	0.28 [-0.36; 0.92]	1.17 [0.66; 1.97]
	Ascending	0.02 [-0.19;0.23]	0.99 [0.70; 1.39]	0.02 [-0.13; 0.16]	0.030 [-0.074;0.135]	0.93 [0.62; 1.37]	-0.04 [-0.70; 0.62]	0.76 [0.38; 1.39]
	Low stable	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
Distance to nearest blue space	High stable	-0.07 [-0.19;0.04]	0.96 [0.80; 1.16]	-0.06 [-0.14;0.02]	-0.024 [-0.079;0.032]	0.88 [0.72; 1.08]	-0.22 [-0.57; 0.12]	0.91 [0.68; 1.24]

Abbreviations: BMI, body mass index; NDVI, normalized difference vegetation index; CI, confidence interval; * p-value < 0.05. β values are regression coefficients (95% confidence interval) from linear regression models, reflecting the change in body mass index z-score, systolic and diastolic blood pressure z-scores, and metabolic syndrome score, for each trajectory as compared to the reference trajectory. OR values are odds ratios (95% confidence interval) from logistic regression models, reflecting the odds of having overweight/obesity, high blood pressure, and metabolic syndrome at 10 years, for each trajectory as compared to the reference trajectory

Table S9. Crude and adjusted linear regression associations of green and blue spaces trajectories with continuous body fat content and fat distribution outcomes at 10 years (n=2623)

		Fat mass index		Android-to-gynoid fat ratio	
		Crude model	Adjusted model	Crude model	Adjusted model
		Exp(β) [95% CI]	Exp(β) [95% CI]	β [95% CI]	β [95% CI]
NDVI 100m	Low ascending	0.96 [0.92; 0.99]	0.97 [0.93; 1.02]	-0.01 [-0.03; 0.00]	-0.01 [-0.02; 0.01]
	High stable	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
NDVI 250m	Low ascending	0.96 [0.92; 0.99]	0.98 [0.94; 1.01]	0.02 [-0.03; 0.00]	-0.01 [-0.03; 0.01]
	Descending	0.95 [0.87; 1.04]	0.97 [0.89; 1.06]	-0.01 [-0.05; 0.02]	-0.01 [-0.04; 0.02]
	Ascending	0.94 [0.87; 1.00]	0.97 [0.90; 1.05]	0.04 [-0.06; -0.01]	-0.03 [-0.05; 0.00]
	High stable	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
NDVI 500m	Low ascending	0.97 [0.94; 1.00]	0.99 [0.95; 1.03]	-0.01 [-0.03; -0.00]	-0.01 [-0.02; 0.01]
	Descending	0.96 [0.89; 1.05]	0.97 [0.89; 1.06]	-0.02 [-0.05; 0.01]	-0.02 [-0.06; 0.01]
	Ascending	0.97 [0.90; 1.03]	1.01 [0.94; 1.09]	-0.02 [-0.05; 0.00]	-0.01 [-0.04; 0.02]
	High stable	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
Distance to nearest green space	Medium stable	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
	Descending	0.99 [0.91; 1.07]	0.99 [0.91; 1.08]	-0.01 [-0.04; 0.03]	-0.00 [-0.04; 0.03]
	Ascending	1.01 [0.93; 1.10]	1.00 [0.92; 1.09]	0.00 [-0.03; 0.03]	-0.00 [-0.03; 0.03]
Distance to nearest blue space	Low stable	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
	High stable	0.98 [0.94; 1.03]	0.98 [0.94; 1.03]	-0.00 [-0.02; 0.02]	-0.00 [-0.02; 0.02]

Abbreviations: NDVI, normalized difference vegetation index; CI, confidence interval; β and Exponential (Exp) β values are regression coefficients and their exponentiation (95% confidence interval) from linear regression models, reflecting the absolute change in android-gynoid index and the relative change in fat mass index, respectively, for each trajectory as compared to the reference trajectory. Adjusted β and exp(β) consider maternal educational level at birth, and neighbourhood deprivation index, nitrogen dioxide (NO₂) and particulate matter less than 2.5 μ m (PM_{2.5}) at birth and at 10 years

Table S10. Adjusted linear regression associations of green and blue spaces, at each time point, with continuous z-scores of metabolic syndrome components at 10 years (n=2731)

		Waist circumference z-scores	Triglycerides z-scores	HDL z-scores	HOMA-IR z-scores	Glucose z-scores
		β [95% CI]				
At birth	NDVI 100m (SD)	0.03 [-0.03;0.08]	-0.02 [-0.05;0.01]	0.01 [-0.03;0.04]	0.02 [-0.03;0.07]	0.02 [-0.01; 0.05]
	NDVI 250 m (SD)	0.01 [-0.06;0.07]	-0.02 [-0.05;0.02]	-0.01 [-0.05;0.03]	-0.01 [-0.07;0.05]	0.00 [-0.04; 0.04]
	NDVI 500m (SD)	-0.01 [-0.08;0.07]	-0.03 [-0.07;0.01]	0.01 [-0.03;0.05]	-0.03 [-0.10;0.03]	-0.02 [-0.06; 0.02]
	Distance to nearest green space (SD)	0.02 [-0.04;0.08]	0.01 [-0.01;0.04]	-0.03 [-0.06; 0.00]	0.04 [-0.01;0.09]	0.01 [-0.02; 0.04]
	Distance to nearest blue space (SD)	0.03 [-0.03;0.08]	-0.01 [-0.03;0.02]	-0.01 [-0.04;0.02]	-0.02 [-0.07;0.02]	-0.03* [†] [-0.06; -0.00]
	NDVI 100m (SD)	0.02 [-0.04;0.08]	-0.02 [-0.05;0.01]	0.00 [-0.03;0.04]	0.02 [-0.03;0.07]	0.02 [-0.00; 0.06]
4 years	NDVI 250 m (SD)	0.03 [-0.03;0.10]	0.01 [-0.04;0.03]	-0.02 [-0.06;0.02]	0.02 [-0.04;0.08]	0.01 [-0.02; 0.05]
	NDVI 500m (SD)	0.03 [-0.04;0.10]	-0.02 [-0.06;0.02]	0.00 [-0.04;0.05]	-0.00 [-0.06; 0.06]	-0.01 [-0.04; 0.03]
	Distance to nearest green space (SD)	0.05 [-0.01;0.10]	0.01 [-0.02;0.04]	-0.02 [-0.05;0.02]	0.06* [†] [0.01;0.11]	0.02 [-0.02; 0.05]
	Distance to nearest blue space (SD)	0.04 [-0.01;0.09]	-0.02 [-0.04;0.01]	-0.01 [-0.04;0.02]	-0.02 [-0.07;0.02]	-0.04* [†] [-0.06; -0.01]
	NDVI 100m (SD)	0.03 [-0.03;0.09]	-0.01 [-0.04;0.02]	0.00 [-0.03;0.03]	-0.01 [-0.07;0.04]	0.01 [-0.02;0.05]
	NDVI 250 m (SD)	0.03 [-0.03;0.10]	0.00 [-0.03;0.04]	-0.02 [-0.06;0.02]	-0.02 [-0.07;0.04]	-0.00 [-0.04; 0.03]
7 years	NDVI 500m (SD)	0.02 [-0.05;0.09]	-0.01 [-0.05;0.02]	-0.01 [-0.05;0.04]	-0.00 [-0.10;0.03]	-0.04 [-0.07;0.01]
	Distance to nearest green space (SD)	0.06 [-0.00;0.11]	0.01 [-0.01;0.04]	-0.02 [-0.06;0.01]	0.05 [-0.00;0.10]	0.02 [-0.01;0.05]
	Distance to nearest blue space (SD)	0.04 [-0.01;0.09]	-0.03* [†] [-0.05; -0.00]	-0.00 [-0.03;0.03]	-0.03 [-0.08;0.02]	-0.04* [†] [-0.07; -0.01]
	NDVI 100m (SD)	0.02 [-0.04;0.08]	0.00 [-0.03;0.03]	-0.02 [-0.05;0.02]	0.02 [-0.03;0.08]	0.02 [-0.02;0.05]
	NDVI 250 m (SD)	0.02 [-0.05;0.09]	0.02 [-0.02;0.05]	-0.04* [†] [-0.08; -0.00]	0.04 [-0.02; 0.10]	0.02 [-0.01;0.06]
	NDVI 500m (SD)	-0.01 [-0.07;0.06]	-0.00 [-0.04;0.03]	-0.01 [-0.05;0.03]	0.02 [-0.04;0.08]	-0.02 [-0.06; 0.02]
10 years	Distance to nearest green space (SD)	0.05 [-0.00;0.11]	0.02 [-0.01;0.05]	-0.02 [-0.06;0.01]	0.05 [0.00;0.10]	0.01 [-0.02;0.04]
	Distance to nearest blue space (SD)	0.03 [-0.02; 0.08]	-0.03 [-0.05;0.00]	-0.01 [-0.04;0.02]	-0.01 [-0.06;0.03]	-0.04* [†] [-0.07; -0.01]

Abbreviations: NDVI, normalized difference vegetation index; CI, confidence interval; SD, standard deviation. * p-value < 0.05; [†] Indicates loss of significance after multiple testing correction. β values are regression coefficients (95% confidence interval) from linear regression models, reflecting the change in waist circumference, triglycerides, HDL, HOMA-IR, and glucose z-scores, per unit of increase of each standard deviation of exposure, at each follow-up. Adjusted β consider maternal educational level at birth, and neighbourhood deprivation index, nitrogen dioxide (NO₂) and particulate matter less than 2.5 μ m (PM_{2.5}) at each respective timepoint

Table S11. Adjusted linear regression associations between green and blue spaces trajectories with continuous z-scores of metabolic syndrome components at 10 years (n=2731)

		Waist Circumference z-scores	Triglycerides z-scores	HDL z-scores	HOMA-IR z-scores	Glucose z-scores
		β [95% CI]				
NDVI 100m	Low ascending	0.01 [-0.15;0.16]	0.01 [-0.07;0.08]	0.01 [-0.08;0.10]	-0.02 [-0.16;0.12]	-0.02 [-0.11;0.06]
	High stable	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
NDVI 250m	Low ascending	0.01 [-0.14;0.15]	0.03 [-0.05;0.10]	0.05 [-0.03;0.13]	0.01 [-0.12;0.14]	0.03 [-0.05;0.11]
	Descending	-0.29 [-0.60;0.02]	-0.16 [-0.05; 0.10]	0.13 [-0.06;0.31]	-0.13 [-0.41;0.16]	0.01 [-0.17;0.19]
	Ascending	-0.00 [-0.28;0.28]	0.10 [-0.05;0.24]	0.04 [-0.13;0.21]	0.00 [-0.25;0.26]	-0.01 [-0.17;0.16]
	High stable	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
NDVI 500m	Low ascending	-0.00 [-0.14;0.14]	0.02 [-0.05;0.09]	0.05 [-0.03;0.13]	0.03 [-0.09;0.16]	0.05 [-0.03;0.12]
	Descending	-0.31* [†] [-0.61;-0.01]	-0.03 [-0.19;0.12]	-0.05 [-0.13;0.22]	-0.18 [-0.45;0.09]	-0.01 [-0.18;0.16]
	Ascending	0.03 [-0.25;0.31]	0.00 [-0.14;0.15]	0.01 [-0.15;0.18]	-0.11 [-0.36;0.14]	-0.08 [-0.23;0.08]
	High stable	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
Distance to nearest green space	Medium stable	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
	Descending	0.03 [-0.28;0.33]	0.05 [-0.11;0.20]	0.04 [-0.13;0.22]	-0.05 [-0.32;0.22]	-0.07 [-0.24;0.10]
Distance to nearest blue space	Ascending	0.00 [-0.29;0.29]	0.08 [-0.07;0.23]	-0.02 [-0.20;0.15]	0.10 [-0.16;0.37]	-0.01 [-0.17;0.16]
	Low stable	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.	Ref.
	High stable	-0.03 [-0.19;0.12]	-0.04 [-0.13;0.04]	-0.04 [-0.13;0.06]	-0.14 [-0.28;0.01]	-0.10* [†] [-0.19; -0.01]

Abbreviations: NDVI, normalized difference vegetation index. CI, confidence interval. * p-value < 0.05; [†] Indicates loss of significance after multiple testing correction. β values are regression coefficients (95% confidence interval) from linear regression models, reflecting the change in waist circumference, triglycerides, HDL, and glucose z-scores, for each trajectory as compared to the reference trajectory. Adjusted β consider maternal educational level at birth, and neighbourhood deprivation index, nitrogen dioxide (NO₂) and particulate matter less than 2.5 μ m (PM_{2.5}) at birth and at 10 years

Residential exposure to green and blue spaces over childhood and cardiometabolic health outcomes

G721
GERAÇÃO 21

Population-based Birth Cohort
n = 4669

EXPOSURE

Normalized difference vegetation index (100m, 250m, 500m)

Residential distance to Green and Blue Spaces

At each time point and as trajectories from birth to 10 years

OUTCOMES

Body Mass Index, Body fat content and distribution, Blood Pressure, Metabolic Outcomes (glucose, insulin, HOMA-IR, HDL, triglycerides, waist circumference)

Limited evidence of associations between urban green/blue spaces and pediatric cardiometabolic outcomes during key developmental periods.